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PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS OF SAR WIND EMULATOR

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ESA SAR OCEAN WIND, WAVES AND CURRENTS

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Introduction

It is realised that the spatial coverage and irregular revisit time of SAR sensors is not adequate for direct use in operational weather forecasting or assimilation into numerical forecast models. Therefore a new way is sought to take benefit from the obvious strength of SAR for high resolution wind speed retrieval. Our aim is to derive some relationships between high resolution SAR wind speed information and lower resolution numerical model output or in situ data, which are regularly available in a real time forecast situation. The algorithm proposed in this study is as follows:

1. Generate mean wind fields for all available SAR images over a region, grouped by a discrete number of "flow types", to be defined
2. Fit a Transfer Function to calculate the high resolution (SAR) wind for each flow type, given a low resolution (model) wind field
3. In real time operation: given a model field (nowcast or forecast), use the transfer function to calculate (emulate) the high resolution wind field

This document summarises the preliminary results at mid term of the project SAR Ocean Wind, Waves and Currents.

Mean Envisat ASAR wind field maps

At NERSC, Envisat ASAR Wide Swath scenes covering the Norwegian coast have been collected routinely from the ESA Rolling Archives since May 2005. Since July 2006, wind speed has been routinely calculated from the SAR scenes, taking the wind direction for the inversion from the NCEP GFS model system. For this study, we have selected two regions each of ~300-400 km size, for derivation of mean wind speed maps. The two study areas are shown on Figure .

Both regions have complex coastlines and topography, and are therefore very challenging for numerical weather forecast models. It is expected that the wind patterns in such regions are highly dependent on the synoptic situation (general wind direction, type of flow, stability etc).

The mean wind from all available ASAR wind products covering the coast of Finnmark in Northern Norway is shown on Figure 1. It is created from more than 300 ASAR scenes, and the mean wind field is quite smooth, showing mean winds of 9-11 m/s offshore, dropping quickly to 5-6 m/s inside the fjords.

Figure 1: Composite ASAR wind speed for the coast of Finnmark in Northern Norway (top). Bottom figures shows the number of ASAR scenes used for creating the composite for each pixel.

More interesting than the overall mean wind speed is when the composite is made separately for different wind regimes, as seen on Figure 2. It is seen that some parts inside and directly outside of the fjords have much higher mean wind speed for some wind directions than others, and that some areas are in a wind shadow with lower wind speeds for some wind directions. Whereas much of the patterns look reasonable and could have been qualitatively anticipated, it is also observed some surprising features where the wind speed is actually higher for the center NCEP wind direction perpendicular to the fjord than along the fjord. This reflects that the real wind direction and speed changes very rapidly within such complex topography. The composite wind speed maps have been shown to local operational weather forecasters, who find the results very interesting. Since there are very few wind measurements in the region, and none at all offshore, the forecasters can not confirm the results, but with their general long term experience the wind patterns are found reasonable, though partly surprising.

The aim and challenge of the wind emulator study is to take benefit from the obvious high resolution information stored in the composite SAR wind fields, for improvement of real time weather forecasts.

Figure 2: Composite wind speed over Finnmark, separated into four different wind direction quadrants. For each subfigure only ASAR wind speed products are used where the corresponding NCEP wind direction at center of the region is within the quadrant bounded by the two arrows. I.e., the upper left figure is the composite wind speed for NCEP wind blowing north-eastwards. Colour scale is the same as for Figure 1.

Figure 3 shows the composite wind for the same region for 12 different large scale (NCEP) wind directions. While this figure reveal more detailed information about for which wind

direction the various fjord jets are “triggered”, it also shows more randomness, where the complex wind patterns of individual SAR scenes are visible. Hence, whereas slightly more than 300 scenes were sufficient to generate a smooth overall mean wind field (Figure 1), even more scenes would be desirable to improve the wind speed statistics for each bin of wind directions. For the given region, about 300 scenes we collected during 1.5 years, so all available SAR scenes over a 3 year period should probably give mean wind speed with sufficient statistical confidence to be useful for the purpose of the wind emulator. At lower latitudes with less frequent SAR coverage, more years would be necessary to collect enough data.

Figure 3: Same as Figure 2, but separate figures for NCEP center wind direction within 12 different bins.

Composite wind speed at wind turbine height

One obvious extension of the SAR surface wind speed composites is to use a boundary layer model to calculate the wind speed at some higher altitude, something which is of high interest to the wind farm communities. In this study we have used a boundary layer model described by Kudryavtsev et al. (2000) and Brown (1982). For each SAR scene, the sea surface temperature and air temperature at 2 m is used to parameterize the boundary layer stability, and the wind speed at 90 m altitude is calculated. Figure shows the composite wind speed at 90 m altitude for a region off the coast of South-Western Norway. The wind speeds agree well with a study based on long term hindcast data (Enova, 2007), but the SAR wind speed is given with a higher spatial resolution.

Figure 4: Composite Envisat ASAR wind speed at 90 m altitude, calculated from standard 10 m cmod-4 wind speed, with a boundary layer model from Kudryavtsev et al. (2000) and Brown (1982). The atmospheric stability is parameterized from sea surface temperature and 2 m air temperature, also taken from the NCEP GFS model for the field closest in time of each SAR scene (max 1.5 hour difference).

Derivation of high resolution transfer functions (Wind Emulator)

To make practical use of the composite SAR winds, we aim to derive some transfer function(s) to correlate this high resolution wind information with forecast model output or in situ data which is readily and reliably available in any forecast situation. As a first very simple step we try to parameterize the wind speed at any point (pixel) in the given region by the NCEP GFS model wind speed and direction at the center point.

$$W_{i,j} = F_{i,j}(windspeed_{NCEP_center}, winddir_{NCEP_center})$$

A simple neural network scheme has been used to fit the transfer function F for some selected test locations shown on Figure 5.

**Figure 5: Selected test sites for fitting of transfer function.
A weather buoy is deployed at the Nordkyn position.**

For the site LoppHAVet the composite ASAR wind speed is strongly dependent on the wind direction (Figure 2 and Figure 3). The transfer function for LoppHAVet is shown on Figure 6 (solid line) together with the individual ASAR wind estimates (dots) to which it is fitted. The transfer function reflects that the wind speed at LoppHAVet increases monotonically with the NCEP speed at the center position, and the wind speed is also found to be lower for wind directions between 150 and 270 degrees (wind blowing from North/North-East), consistent with Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 6: ASAR wind speed versus NCEP centre wind speed (top) and direction (bottom). The solid lines show the transfer function fitted versus the same data, where wind direction is held fixed at 90 degrees on upper figure and wind speed is held fixed at 10 m/s on bottom figure.

Despite some good qualitative agreement, Figure 6 also shows that there is a large scatter in the ASAR wind speeds, and that it is impossible to fit a transfer function to match all individual wind estimates. Some of the scatter must be due to the randomness in the ASAR wind speeds arising from errors in the NCEP model wind direction used for the SAR wind inversion. Some recent tests suggests that the regional high resolution (10 km) HIRLAM model gives better wind directions than the global coarser resolution NCEP model. Thus we will reprocess the SAR wind speeds with HIRLAM directional information, hopefully decreasing the scatter around the fitted transfer function. We hope also to capitalise on future progress on using a Bayesian approach for wind retrieval (combined use of FFT and model for wind direction) and use of the SAR Doppler information for direction ambiguity removal. We will also experiment with using the boundary layer stability as a parameter in the neural network. This idea is encouraged by the local forecasters who look closely at the stability when making subjective forecasts, as the stability may determine in some cases whether the main flow will go over or around the topography. To use only the model wind information at the center of the region may also be too simplistic, and we will experiment with using several model points as input parameters, and also perform a sensitivity test on the radius of influence from the model reference points. The transfer functions fitted to the three other sites (Nordkyn, SiteA and SiteB on Figure 5) show a close relation to the model wind speed, but less dependency on the model wind direction (Figures not shown here). Hence much of the directional dependency on the wind speed seen for these sites on Figure 2 and Figure 3 may be caused by generally stronger winds from particular directions. Thus the usefulness of the wind emulator will be mainly very close to the coast and within fjords and coastal basins.

Summary and future work

Composite wind speed maps based on Envisat ASAR have been made for some Norwegian coastal regions with complex fjord topography. The wind direction for the SAR wind inversion has been taken from the global NCEP GFS model system. Composites have also been made separately for different model wind directions, and a strong dependency of the high resolution SAR wind speed on the lower resolution model wind direction is found. This suggests that the SAR composite wind contains useful information that may be used to add spatial detail to lower resolution operational numerical weather forecasts. A first attempt has been made to parameterise the SAR wind speed from the speed and direction from the model. A derived transfer function is seen to reproduce the main features, but a large scatter is found where individual wind estimates deviate much from the fitted values. Several possible means to improve the transfer functions are suggested:

- increase accuracy of SAR wind retrieval by using regional high resolution forecast model (HIRLAM) instead of global model, and eventually take benefit from bayesian wind direction retrieval and SAR Doppler information,
- incorporate information about boundary layer stability,
- investigate the spatial correlation between model output and the SAR wind.

SAR data collected over a site for a time period of 2-3 years seems to be necessary/sufficient to develop a wind emulator.

High resolution composite SAR wind at wind turbine height (e.g. 90 m) is a bi-product that can be useful for the wind energy community.

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